

840 cm^{-1} , respectively^{8,9}. Upon complexation the ν_{N-O} centered in the region 1230–1222 cm^{-1} . This lowering of the ν_{NO} was in accordance with O-complexation in all these complexes¹⁰. In most of the complexes, δ_{NO} appearing in the region 830–820 cm^{-1} indicates that it was lowered by some 20–10 cm^{-1} ; this further supported of the coordination through the oxygen. The C—H out-of-plane vibration of the ligand shifted to a higher wave number by 10 cm^{-1} in the complexes due to decrease in the electron density in the aromatic ring as a consequence of ligand to metal charge transfer. The 400–385 cm^{-1} band are tentatively assigned to $\nu_{Ln-O}^{11,12}$. In all the thiocyanato complexes the N-bonded mode of coordination of thiocyanato group^{11,12} was confirmed by the appearance of the bands at \sim 2025, 790 and 470 cm^{-1} , assigned to ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCB} , respectively.

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Extraction of Titanium(IV) from Acidic Thiocyanate Solution by Tri-isoamyl Phosphate

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AMONG the phosphatic solvents trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO), diethylhexylphosphoric acid (DEHPA) and tri-n-butyl phosphate (TBP) have been successfully utilised for the extraction of Ti^{IV} from aqueous acidic solutions^{1,2}. Tri-isoamyl phosphate (TAP), an indigenous solvent prepared from fusel oil and a by-product of Indian alcohol industry, has been used for the extraction of Ti^{IV} from its aqueous hydrochloric acid solutions³.

Experimental

Tri-isoamyl phosphate (TAP) was prepared by the standard method as reported earlier³. Stock solution of Ti^{IV} was prepared by digesting potassium titanyl oxalate in concentrated hydrochloric acid and heating with concentrated nitric acid in order to remove the oxalate. Ti^{IV} content of the stock solution was determined spectrophotometrically by the H_2O_2 method⁴. Experimental solutions of Ti^{IV} were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. All other reagents were of A.R. grade.

The solvent (15 ml) was equilibrated with an equal volume of the aqueous layer having the desired acidity but no Ti^{IV} . The pre-equilibrated solvent (10 ml) was equilibrated with an equal volume of aqueous layer containing requisite amount of sodium thiocyanate and appropriate amount of Ti^{IV} in a stoppered measuring cylinder.

Concentration of hydrogen ion in the aqueous and organic phase (by back-extraction into deionised water) in all the experiments was determined by potentiometric titration with standard alkali. The concentrations of thiocyanate ion and Ti^{IV} in the organic phase were estimated spectrophotometrically⁴. Carbon tetrachloride was invariably used as a diluent because it was completely miscible with TAP. Initial experiments had shown that a 33% solution of TAP gave maximum extraction of Ti^{IV} and a further increase in the concentration of extractant did not increase the distribution ratio.

Results and Discussion

The effect of variation of $[\text{SCN}]^-$ at an arbitrarily fixed $[\text{HCl}]$ of 5.0 M showed that the distribution coefficient increases with increasing thiocyanate ion concentration and was maximum at $[\text{SCN}]^- = 1.8 \text{ M}$; further increase in $[\text{SCN}]^-$ had no effect.

Though Ti^{IV} is hydrolysed in dilute acidic solution yet hydrolysis is not anticipated at an acidity of $\geq 4.0 M$. The extraction of Ti^{IV} below $4.0 M$ hydrochloric acid concentration was found to be poor presumably due to the presence of several inextractable hydrolysed Ti^{IV} species. On increasing the hydrochloric acid concentration above $4.0 M$, the extraction coefficient increased sharply and 97.5% extraction of Ti^{IV} was registered at $6.0 M$ HCl. The $[Ti^{IV}] : [SCN]^-$ molar ratio in the organic phase corresponds to $Ti(SCN)_4$ in each set of the experiment with 4.0 to $\geq 6.0 M$ HCl acidity in the aqueous phase.

In order to determine the solvation number of the extracted species, solutions of TAP of varying concentration in carbon tetrachloride were used to extract Ti^{IV} at $6.0 M$ HCl (Table 1). A plot of log (distribution coefficient) vs log TAP gave a straight line with a slope of 1.99, indicating thereby that two molecules of TAP were associated with the extracted species.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF TAP CONCENTRATION ON THE EXTRACTION OF Ti^{IV} FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION $6.0 M$ IN HCl

$[Ti^{IV}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[SCN]^- = 1.8 M$
Vol. of aq. layer = vol. of org. layer = 10 ml

TAP %	$[Ti^{IV}]_{aq} \times 10^{-3} M$	$[Ti^{IV}]_{org} \times 10^{-3} M$	D	E
2.0	101.1	186.9	1.85	64.99
5.0	77.6	210.4	2.70	73.03
12.0	22.6	265.4	11.76	92.16
15.0	19.7	268.3	13.65	93.17
17.0	17.5	270.5	15.42	93.91
20.0	14.4	273.6	19.00	95.00
22.0	13.1	274.9	21.05	95.46
25.0	9.5	278.5	29.15	96.68
30.0	8.2	279.8	34.42	97.18
33.0	7.1	280.9	39.15	97.50
35.0	7.1	280.9	39.15	97.50
40.0	7.1	280.9	39.15	97.50

$$D = [Ti^{IV}]_{org} / [Ti^{IV}]_{aq}, E = 100 D / (D + 1).$$

Separation of Ti^{IV} from Zr^{IV} solutions: A solution containing equivalent amounts of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} in $6.0 M$ HCl was extracted with 33% TAP solution in a 1:1 mixture of CCl_4 and hexanol. It was observed that 96.5% of Zr^{IV} was left in the aqueous phase while 85% of the Ti^{IV} was extracted into the organic layer in a single operation.

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Aromatic Nucleophilic Substitution Reaction between 1-Fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene and *p*-Substituted-aniline—A Kinetic Approach

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KINETICS of the reaction between 1-halo-2,4-dinitrobenzene and aromatic amines have been carried out through volumetric, potentiometric and spectrophotometric techniques¹⁻⁴. Since one of the products formed in the title reaction is a strong electrolyte, an attempt was made to study the kinetics of the above reaction conductometrically at three different temperatures in acetonitrile and the second order rate constant was evaluated. An attempt was also made to correlate the effect of the substituents in the *para*-position of the nucleophile through Hammett equation. Nature of the products obtained was confirmed by ir, nmr and uv spectra. From nmr spectral data, orientation of rings during substitution was evaluated.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in acetonitrile. 1-Fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene was re-purified by crystallisation from ether to constant melting point (26°). Aniline was purified by steam distillation, the fraction distilling between 180 and 184° was collected. *p*-Chloroaniline and *p*-bromoaniline were prepared following standard procedures⁵. Commercial samples of *p*-toluidine and *p*-anisidine were purified by recrystallisation to constant melting point.

The reaction was followed conductometrically in a bottle type conductivity cell kept in a thermostat ($\pm 0.015^\circ$). The conductance was recorded using a Pico conductivity bridge at appropriate regular intervals of time. The infinite reading was taken after 48 h.

Results and Discussion

The values of rate constants at different temperatures and activation parameters are reported in Table 1. The rate of the reaction was found to